

UDC 159.9.37:017.92:371.1

DOI: 10.15587/2519-4984.2022.253615

THE PROBLEM OF DETERMINING THE FEATURES OF UNDERSTANDING THE CONCEPT OF "SPIRITUAL CULTURE" AS A COMPONENT OF SELF-REALIZATION OF PERSONALITY

Larisa Likhitska, Lesya Starovoit

The article examines the impact of national and cultural values on socialization of a personality and its spiritual development. Main attention is related to the problem of education of value orientation, such as spiritual, human, national with have a significant influence on human socialization.

Purpose. *Spiritual development of the person includes a system of ethical values and national cultural landmarks, which are implemented in the subjective selection of ideals, objective rating system and specific human behavior. One of the most important is a problem of education and preservation of spiritual values of the younger generation, cultural and spiritual values, which are the basis of human existence.*

Methods *The article analyzes the views of scientists to determine the spiritual values of national culture. They are formed during the historical development of the nation, development of its material and spiritual culture.*

Results. *The current period of society development requires new approaches to education and future generations. A measure of social development has always been a measure of cultural and spiritual nature of human.*

Originality. *Significant attention is given to nurturing influence of family in the formation of spiritual potential of a personality.*

Conclusion. *The biggest impact of all processes contradictions that occur suffers from, primarily, the family as the most important center of society. Changes, occurring in our country, promote the growth of the family role in the morality formation of the younger generation. It is saying about the impact of national and cultural values, which change in the formation of spiritual culture*

Keywords: *spirituality, spiritual education of student's personality, spiritual education, humanization*

How to cite:

Likhitska, L., Starovoit, L. (2022). The problem of determining the features of understanding the concept of "spiritual culture" as a component of self-realization of personality. ScienceRise: Pedagogical Education, 1 (46), 28–32. doi: <http://doi.org/10.15587/2519-4984.2022.253615>

© The Author(s) 2021

This is an open access article under the Creative Commons CC BY license hydrate

1. Introduction

The specificity of spiritual culture is that it cannot be "imposed" on a person. This is explained by the fact that it appears as a complex of spiritual wealth, which is mastered by an individual on the basis of selective attitude to it. That is why the principle of spiritual freedom is a prerequisite that allows us to make this choice without harming both an individual and society. In the process of self-development in an individual there must be a need to self-improve, to evolve responsibly to realize their spiritual strength. In fact, the spiritual life of an individual is defined as "a special active way of human development of the world, including the entire external world – nature and society, and the inner world of human him/herself in terms of his/her formation and development" [1, 2]. The basis for this method of development is spirituality as the inner core of an individual, which sets the direction of all life and self-realization in particular. Therefore, spiritual culture is a special area of interaction between society and an individual in the process of self-realization of the latter. It is in this area that the socio-cultural determination of the freedom of self-realization

reveals integrity as one of the main characteristics of the latter. What is the role of spirituality in the process of self-realization of an individual? This is the problem of devaluation of universal values, the state of public consciousness in general and an individual in particular; and a change in priorities in creative activity – the replacement of real creativity (by inspiration) by "creativity to order", the value of which is measured primarily by the amount of investment. This issue includes the imaginary freedom of choice, when a person is asked to choose from a variety of "cheap" in depth of content and not very cheap in price goods of "mass spiritual production". We should also mention the dominance of mass culture, which penetrates everywhere: on TV screens, in cinemas, on the pages of printed publications, in concert activities. It is also a loss of confidence both in the very ideals of society and in the possibilities of their implementation; and, on the one hand, fascination with foreign, "alien" culture, a thoughtless attempt to introduce its fashion trends on national soil, and on the other – one-sided, banal primitive use of national cultural heritage. Among the problems of development of spiritual culture is the

problem of development of spiritual culture of an individual, as well as the constructive role of the state and social institutions in overcoming negative phenomena in this area and preventing their further spread. After all, the spirituality of an individual is not limited to his/her inner spiritual world. It can also include the immediate path of life and self-realization. The expression of self-realization is the integrity of human, which in philosophical studies is associated primarily with its uniqueness and originality [3]. Thus, the condition of the latter, and hence the integrity of human is his/her autonomy. Thus, spirituality in the imagination, images, projections of one's own future gives a person the freedom to constantly remove any socio-cultural restrictions in order to reveal their true humanistic individual essence and to carry out holistic personal self-realization.

2. Literary review

Teachers interpret spirituality as the inner strength of an individual, the core of life, the hierarchy of universal values, creativity according to the laws of beauty. These works are, in particular, about the development of spiritual meanings [4], the character traits of human as a bearer of spirituality [5], the spiritual potential of human and the possibility of knowing the phenomena of spirituality [6], the specific features of the phenomenon of spirituality. faith and religion [7]. The dominant process of human spiritual development determines such components as truth, goodness and beauty. Spirituality is seen as a concept that reflects values and meanings. A component of spiritual development is the education of the soul and self-realization of an individual. The vast majority of researchers consider the self, which in philosophical and psychological research is considered as:

- the system of human ideas about themselves;
- an integrating center that unites the systems of the psyche;
- "organizer" of human activity, aimed at self-change, self-development, self-realization, as the system-creating factor or "organizer" of human as an integrity

Studies of those scientists who reveal the role of "will to meaning" to understand the issues worth living for, realizing fateful values in creative work, are important for understanding the nature of spirituality [9].

Even a very brief review of works on the problem of spirituality shows that the process of spiritual development is a gradual approach to the top morally relevant heights. Spirituality should be considered in dynamics as a life-changing process [9, 10]. This phenomenon is determined by the peculiarities of the promotion of an individual in the hierarchy of values and mastery of spiritual culture. In fact, this is a sign of spiritual development and self-realization of an individual.

The analysis of literary sources suggests that the concepts of "spirituality", "spiritual culture" are important elements of modern scientific and pedagogical discourse.

3. Research aim and tasks

The aim of the article is to define the term "spiritual culture" in the process of self-realization of an individual as a prerequisite for his/her formation, when a person, carrying out free, active transformational activi-

ties, learns the spiritual heritage of mankind as a subject of culture.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks were set:

1. To consider the main approaches to the definition of culture and its functions, to put forward own interpretation of this concept.
2. To determine the system of values that should be used in the formation of spiritual culture, based on the analysis of the concepts of "spirituality" and "development".
3. To describe the main components of spiritual culture.
4. To develop a sound methodology for the formation and implementation of the term "spiritual culture" in the process of self-realization of a person.

4. Materials and methods

The theoretical and methodological basis of the study is the use of theoretical provisions of the structural-functional paradigm: the theory of social change, the concept of cultural trauma, sociology of everyday life, which allowed to consider spiritual culture as a structured social phenomenon that determines cultural and civilizational progress.

To solve the research tasks, a set of general scientific methods was used, which provide logic and systematic research, in particular: analysis and synthesis (to determine and systematize the theoretical and methodological foundations of research on values), comparison (to identify and compare existing scientific approaches to interpretation of concepts of "personality" and "spirituality"), classification (to systematize the factors of classification of different types of values, including spiritual).

5. Results

Personal growth is an active process of formation, in which a person takes responsibility for his/her life, his/her life path. We constantly feel the influence of needs, aspirations, plans, dreams, ambitions, generated from within our being. The level of human integrity is determined by the degree of integration of the qualities of an individual, personality and subject as different levels of the internal organization of human with the self as an integrative center. A special form of being an integral person is individuality.

On the effective side, self-realization is the result of the formation of a person's creative individuality, which overcomes the contradictions between its ancestral essence and the uniqueness of an individual. At the same time, as a subject of life, a person strives for "acme-culmination" [9] or for a way of self-realization of the subject of life. This state of personality is somatic, physiological, psychological and social, characterized by maturity of its development, achieving the highest performance. In activity, creativity, spirituality, a person can achieve the state of acme and ultimately self-fulfillment, self-realization only in the course of self-development.

At different ages, we see how our lives are changing due to favorable or, conversely, destructive external circumstances. If we treat an individual as a real dynamic human being, which determines his/her tendency to behave in certain way under certain circumstances and add that each individual is often in the situations, in which

he/she wants to get, then personal development in self-realization will be considered as personal action, largely dependent on the person him/herself. That is, it is about the most important task of life, to meet the basic needs of life, namely "spiritual culture". The adequate influence of spiritual values on the process of self-realization of an individual crucially determines the success of any social actors - from an individual to humanity as a whole. In cultural anthropology, such a status of culture is called a "total social fact." Thus, the influence of spiritual culture on the development of society through the formation of the value environment of socialization determines its anticipatory and prognostic functions in relation to the development of civilization in the XXI century. It "represents a set of value-semantic, information-cognitive, artistic and figurative phenomena that are objectified and developed within the social, group and individual consciousness." At the personal level in the process of self-realization of an individual spiritual culture forms such a quality as human spirituality, the latter should be interpreted as a defining component of spiritual culture, which determines a person's attitude to nature, society, him/herself.

Considering the relationship between personal self-realization and spiritual culture, we focused on two processes. Spiritually-productive activity ensures the formation of spiritual values, and spiritual-practical activity concerns the mastery of spiritual values, accumulated by mankind and social groups in the process of their own cultural development. It is the second process that is defined as the one that underlies the self-realization of an individual and is of the greatest importance for the formation of spiritual values. The result is the acquisition of personal spiritual experience, the development of value orientations, spiritual needs and spiritual feelings. Thus, spiritual culture acts as a product and way of human activity, which, in the process of transforming the world around, transforms itself.

Analyzing the spiritual dimension of the process of self-realization of an individual, it was determined, that the characteristic of the imperatives of spiritual development at the personal level is the influence of certain socio-cultural factors. The process of self-realization was considered primarily as spiritual education, as the formation of personal harmony of the soul with the world, as well as the establishment of spiritual values of truth, goodness, beauty, complemented by other moral absolutes, such as dignity, faith, hope, love. Studying the criteria for the formation of an individual as a spiritual subject, we have outlined a special desire for the spiritual and moral universal ideal.

Assessing the spiritual development of an individual, we studied the problems, associated with the mechanism of formation of spiritual culture at the personal level, creating a socio-cultural and educational environment conducive to spiritual growth, determining the motivational bases and problematic aspects of this process. The substantiation of regularities and tendencies in the field of formation of spirituality of an individual was determined by the peculiarities of actualization of spiritual values both at different age stages and depending on the conditions of self-realization of the individual.

Emphasis was placed on the fact that spiritual culture directly determines the spiritual orientation of an individual, which is embodied in spiritual interests, values, orientations and worldview, manifested in the presence of faith, beliefs, ideals and other spiritual regulations and relies on will, spiritual sensuality and worldview, inherent in an individual in the process of self-development. The essence of the process of self-development as the acquisition of spiritual culture is the acquisition of meaning in the form of established at the personal level value-semantic life landmarks, carried out on the basis of transforming the universe of external being into the inner world of an individual, its creation as an independent entity in the form of combining the image of the world with the moral foundations of personal existence.

The identified intersections of problem fields in the study of spiritual factors of self-realization of an individual by social philosophy and other fields of knowledge requires a solution to the problem of socio-philosophical subjectivity of the concept of "spiritual culture". In practical terms, the problem of socio-philosophical analysis of the concept is of particular importance because it is directly related to the formation of a high level of moral and psychological state as part of self-realization of an individual, which depends on the future of the country in all dimensions – from economic competitiveness to national and cultural self-identification of people. Ultimately, this issue must be resolved through the development of conceptual approaches to research and on this basis – to identify the essence of the concept and determine the direction of solving problems, directly related to the spiritual development of an individual. The context for understanding the foundations of the spiritual formation of an individual is philosophical interpretations of his/her spiritual essence of human and ways to immerse him/herself in the cultural space of his/her people. In this sense, spiritual culture provides the basis for philosophical understanding of the human essence in human, as well as the relationship between human and the world.

In our opinion, the socio-philosophical discourse of the study of understanding the concept of "spiritual culture" as a component of self-realization of an individual should be the issue of mutual determination of personal spiritual development and spiritual life of society as a whole. Spiritual culture unfolds in two forms, which characterize the dominance of personal-activity and socio-cultural components. In the first case we are talking about the formation of spiritual qualities of human and the activity of their objectification, in the second – about the spiritual values that are created by human in the process of his/her self-development and became the property of society. Problems of spiritual formation of human are the subject of socio-philosophical discourse in the context, in which he/she acts as a being capable of self-development. And it is the dimension of self-development that is the phenomenon of spiritual evolution as a consequence of the interaction of an individual and society should be at the center of socio-philosophical analysis.

In our opinion, the specificity of the analysis of the spiritual dimension of the process of self-development is determined by the fact that we are talking about the spiritual world of an individual. Accordingly, the analysis of the spiritual world of an individual is

associated with the process of its formation in terms of the possibility of conscious choice of value alternatives. It is also important, that the spiritual development of an individual in the process of self-development is crucial for the formation of the future of culture.

Accordingly, socio-philosophical analysis should focus on the one hand on the problems of transformation of universal spiritual values into personal meaningful life priorities of personal development, and on the other – on impacts of innovative transformations of his/her spiritual culture on the process of designing social change.

Thus, the concept of "spiritual culture" as a component of self-realization of an individual in its spiritual dimension gives meaning to human existence in the totality of its manifestations, and thus determines its role in the process of self-development of the individual. The result of the spiritual dimension of the process of self-realization is the acquisition by a person of spiritual experience, the development of value orientations, spiritual needs and spiritual feelings. The essence of spiritual self-development is the acquisition of the meaning of life in the form of life guidelines, established on personal level values. At the heart of the socio-philosophical discourse of the study of this phenomenon is the problem of the relationship and interdetermination of personal spiritual development and the spiritual life of society

The most important is the projective and modeling direction of socio-philosophical study of spiritual formation as a component of self-realization of an individual, when it is considered in the context of social development potential.

The range of problems of moral and ethical formation of an individual, his/her socialization, actualization of his/her spiritual resources is covered as widely as possible, because in this case we are talking about the driving forces of global socio-cultural transformations of the post-modern model. Revealing the meaning of the concept of "spiritual culture" as a component of self-realization, the formation of personality, we must first explore its system-creating potential for social development.

The study of the concepts of spiritual culture, spirituality and spiritual and moral education as a component of self-realization of an individual, carried out within the framework of this article, is not exhaustive. Promising areas of further research may be to clarify the forms and means of spiritual and moral education of an individual, as well as the definition and justification of other pedagogical conditions for the formation of spiritual and moral security of an individual in modern conditions.

6. Conclusions

1. In the process of self-realization of an individual, the spiritual culture of society is a prerequisite for its formation as a free, active behavior, as a result of which a person learns the spiritual heritage of mankind as a subject of culture. It gives an individual the opportunity to choose virtually unlimited spiritual values that best meet his/her aspirations and values. The spirituality of an individual expresses his/her ability to grow cultural heritage and self-creation, which implies the presence of freedom in the process of holistic self-realization of the individual, adequate to his/her spiritual needs. This reveals spirituality as the main, basic factor of self-realization of an individual.

2. Spirituality, which is based on the hierarchy of value orientations and meaning-life guidelines of an individual, determines the nature of self-realization of the individual, which manifests itself as an internal external structure. An important determinant of the integrity of human self-realization is the degree of individual desire for such a kind of spiritual self-disclosure as the discovery of "human essence in human."

3. The ability to go beyond the influence of external determinants is realized through the ability of an individual to transcendent mastery of the world. Thanks to this developed ability, an individual in the process of self-realization tries to go beyond his/her own experience and get closer to the absolute subject in order to find reliable support for everything that exists.

4. In the process of self-realization of an individual, the spiritual culture of society is a prerequisite for its formation as a free, active behavior, as a result of which a person learns the spiritual heritage of mankind as a subject of culture. It gives an individual the opportunity to choose virtually unlimited spiritual values that best meet his/her aspirations and values. The spirituality of an individual expresses his/her ability to grow cultural heritage and self-creation, which implies the presence of freedom in the process of holistic self-realization of the individual, adequate to his/her spiritual needs. This reveals spirituality as the main, basic factor of self-realization of an individual. Spirituality, which is based on the hierarchy of value orientations and meaningful life guidelines of an individual, determines the nature of self-realization of the individual, which manifests itself as an internal external structure. An important determinant of the integrity of self-realization of an individual is the degree of human desire for such a kind of spiritual self-disclosure as the discovery of "human essence in human."

References

1. Bekh, I. D. (2003). *Vykhovannia osobystosti. Osobystisno-orientovanyi pidkhdid: naukovo-praktychni zasady*. Kyiv: Lybid, 344.
2. Vasyliuk, R. A. (2014). *Dukhovnyi svit suchasnoi ukrainkoii molodi: aspekty, problemy, perspektyvy*. Available at: <https://urok.osvita.ua/materials/education/38899/>
3. Vysotska, A. M. (2010). *Osnovni napriamy diialnosti vykhovatelya spetsialnoho navchalnoho zakladu dla rozumovo vidstalykh ditei. Aktualni problemy navchannia ta vykhovannia liudei z osoblyvymy potrebamy*, 7, 246–254. Available at: http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/apnvlop_2010_7_35
4. Voronkova, V. H. (2000). *Metafizychni vymiry liudskoho buttia (problemy liudyny na zlami tysiacholit)*. Zaporizhzhia: Pavel, 176.
5. Voronkova, V. H. (2012). *Filosofiiia rozvytku suchasnoho suspilstva: teoretyko-metodolohichni kontekst*. Zaporizhzhia: RVV ZDIA, 262.
6. Hryva, I. A. (2014). *Formuvannia zahalnoliudskykh moralnykh tsinnosti, dukhovnyi rozvytok uchniv na urokakh movy ta literatury, pryrodoznavstva*. Shostka, 89.
7. Desiatnyk, K. (2016). *Dukhovnist osobystosti: aksiolohichni vymiry*. *Skhidnoevropeiskyi natsionalnyi universytet imeni Lesi Ukrainky. Pedahohichni chasopys Volyni*, 2 (3).

-
8. Ziaziun, I. A. (2003). Dukhovna elita u suspilstvi: intelihentnist i hromadianskist. Problemy ta perspektyvy formuvannia natsionalnoi humanitarno-tekhnichnoi elity, 1 (5), 32–41.
9. Melnyk, V. V. (2011). Sotsialno-filosofskyi analiz vzaiemovplyvu i vzaiemodii osobystosti i hlobalizovanoho sotsiumu. Humanitarnyi visnyk Zaporizkoi derzhavnoi inzhenernoi akademii, 46, 96–108.
10. Deutsch, K. W. (2019). Tides among Nations. New York: Free Press, 301–305.

Received date 16.12.2021

Accepted date 18.01.2021

Published date 31.01.2021

Larisa Likhitska*, PhD, Associate Professor, Department of Art Disciplines of Preschool and Primary Education, Vinnytsia Mykhailo Kotsiubynskyi State Pedagogical University, Ostrozkoho str., 56, Vinnitsa, Ukraine, 21001

Lesya Starovoit, PhD, Associate Professor, Head of Department, Department of Art Disciplines of Preschool and Primary Education, Vinnytsia Mykhailo Kotsiubynskyi State Pedagogical University, Ostrozkoho str., 56, Vinnitsa, Ukraine, 21001

**Corresponding author: Larisa Likhitska, e-mail: larisasporish@gmail.com*